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Innovation and technology management: investigate how organizations manage innovation and stay competitive in the modern business landscape

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Abstract

The goal of this study is to emphasize growing sectors of management of innovation topics, and also to provide a summary on the most essential themes and objectives for academic investigation and managerial practice. It continually brings to fresh responses, fresh concepts, or novel forms of business. Each modern dance business's core competitive edge appears in its ability to create its own firm. The purpose of the piece is to emphasize the crucial role of innovation in the operation of today's corporations. Operations founded on innovations have an essential function for promoting affluence and developing and preserving a competitive advantage. The state to play of the Indian IT sector, with a strong focus on innovation-driven company models, indicates that the present time may be an ideal time to perform this investigation.

Keywords: IT Industry; Innovation Management; Business; Modern Organizations; Operations

1. Introduction

An innovation has played an unavoidably central and controlling role in culture, with conflicting outcomes: fortune on the one hand, but also being jobless, ecology deviations, and other issues related to society on the other hand.

Manufacturing methods and manufacturing companies have been selected in all nations in accordance with the specific desires of the involved companies despite the fact that the actual needs in each population can be somewhat distinct.

A study on innovation has been performed in both civilized and underdeveloped nations (Lema, Kraemer-Mbula, & Rakas, 2021). A summary of the surviving writing demonstrates that by far most of study centres around endlessly industrialized countries. On relative fundamental issues, the writing on complete assessments connected with advancement in countries that are as yet creating is confined.

Economically, sectoral, local formal, and individual kinds of invention can all emerge. Entrepreneur and large-firm innovations are fuelled through people with imaginations. Creative enterprises produce neighborhood and cluster-level efficiency, which in turn propel an economy as a whole.

In regard to providing openings for employment, technological advances, growing service sectors, increasing exports, and making world standing, the value of creative thinking in driving a complete industry is crucial. This is gradually acknowledged by developing-country authorities. The President of India announced the decade 2010-2020 to be the Decade of creativity, marking a shift in priority from a driven by knowledge to a creativity-driven business (Dutta, 2012).

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1.1. Strategic Management of Strategic Management of Technology and Innovation

One normal element that has arisen in last 3 forty years is the pace of progress saw in the vast majority of the ventures. The pace of progress in the cutthroat scene is fuelled by development, which comes as innovation and can definitely impact and disturb industry design and contest (OECD, 2016).

Technologies have been found to be as important in both establishing and existing companies, while the stage where it has the greatest effect differs amongst the two (Verhoef, et al., 2021). It has more of an effect on the launch and growth phase of developing businesses, and it serves as a primary competing instrument in mature fields (Farida & Setiawan, 2022).

Previously, a line of inquiry for innovative researchers has been centred on the size of companies. Large businesses with plenty of money demand innovations to expand into novel markets and populations of customers and to keep improving efficiency in operations.

Small enterprises rely on innovations to create distinctive characteristics that will help them reach a critical mass (Taneja, Pryor, & Hayek, 2016). An innovation is the very cause for the continued existence of start-up and entrepreneur-driven companies (Lee, Kim, & Sung, 2019).

Researchers defined innovation in different scenarios in a variety of ways. The OSLO Manual, which gives governs on carrying out Community Invention Studies (CIA) across the European Union, offers a frequently cited to definition. The information that follows is the meaning:

"In business procedures, organization at work, or outside interactions, innovation is the introduction of an entirely novel or significantly better offering (excellent or commodity), manipulate, a novel advertising method, or a new management method."

2. Literature review

Innovation management is now a key part of keeping a competitive edge in modern businesses. Successful innovation management is key to getting a competitive edge that lasts. Companies that do a good job of managing innovation are more likely to come up with and use new products, services, and processes that make them stand out from the competition. By making themselves stand out through innovation, companies can better meet customer wants, increase business efficiency, and, in the end, make more money (Vijay, Mohanraj, & Thirumalai, 2023).

In the current business world, organizations have to handle innovation to stay competitive. The goal of the article is to show how important new ideas are to the success of modern businesses. Operations that are built on innovation are a key part of building and keeping a competitive edge and fostering economic growth. A key part of a successful and efficient organization is that each organizational unit takes part in the process of creation. Innovations aren't just the duty of the R&D, marketing, and production departments; they require the work of all the departments in an organization at the same time (Janjić & Radjenovic, 2019).

It is very important to take a broad approach to all of the things that affect the innovation management process. Getting the right technology and management is an important part of innovation management, but the organization's people and structure are also becoming more important in terms of innovation performance. In a global market where companies have to compete with each other, organizational and management changes are the keys to success. Technology and research and development efforts have had a big impact on the organization's structure and culture, but the right way to handle innovation gives a business an edge (Dereli, 2015).

The goal of innovation economy is to leverage the good in human creative thinking in order to accomplish dynamic productivity, which results in shifting habit advancement of customer choices in marketplaces, as well as high quality / performance for the products and services used by the actors in the economy. In spite of the concerns and worries that innovation may cause, given its abilities of imaginatively destroying existing ideas or product Being in the market, it can still be viewed as a way forward in accumulating wealth and increasing welfare chances for those willing to take on change in an environment of intense rivalry (Ahlstrom, 2010).

Innovative thinking, particularly environmentally friendly innovations (eco-innovation), is an essential component of contemporary economic systems. The aim of this article is to analyze resource effectiveness indicators in light of the extent of green innovation in EU nations. The investigation focuses on the challenges of quantifying green innovation

based on a review of the current research. This article emphasizes the issues related to evaluating eco-innovation, based on a study of the available research on the subject (Berkhout, 2011).

2.1. Research Objective

- To fully comprehend the forces driving innovation in modest IT businesses.
- To examine the link among innovation and achievement in small IT businesses.

3. Method

This study takes into consideration companies that remain in operation for a period of more than three years. In keeping to prior studies, the currency of inventions was deemed crucial, since inventiveness (both products and process) launched just in the recent period in question have been included for investigation. For the evaluation of Firm Achievement, a developed themselves scale was used with revenue growth, earnings, new customer growth, and employee development as the main variables.

3.1. Design of Research

The study's unit of analysis is the company itself. The study used a Diagnostic/ interpretive design of research to examine theories that had been developed (Shea & Yanow, 2011). This is a study that is cross-sectional, so data from the sample organizations was obtained only once.

This study touched on 'small businesses,' one of the initial questions that needed being addressed was what constitutes a tiny company in the Indian IT marketplace.

3.2. Sample design

The research concentrates on tiny Indian IT businesses. The number of people includes of all Indian micro IT businesses. The firm is the Sample Division.

3.3. Quantitative research

This survey was given to a wide group of people, all of whom had at least a decade of experience in the IT service business. This guaranteed that the reply was not only aware of the situation but also had enough experience to have their own opinion on the issue. The target population had to be large enough that even with a low response rate, a statistically meaningful number of replies were accessible for analysis. The survey was administered using appropriate software for polling and a questionnaire tool (Klaas & Baggaley, 2003).

4. Results

4.1. Profiles Study of the Examined Organizations and Participants

The responding organizations were from five South Indian urban communities: the urban areas of Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai, India Thiruvananthapuram, and Kochi. The survey showed two individual members from every one of the organizations. The following part describes a number of company features, ranging such as their ages, size, and line of business grouping, in addition to the primary response characteristics.

4.2. The businesses' ages

The ages of the employees investigated fell between 20 to 45 years, with an average of minimal over twenty one years old table1.

Table 1 Ages of the employees

Age	20-25	25-30	30-35	35-40	40-45
Frequency	10	11	25	57	102

Source: Field Survey

4.3. The company's size

The businesses polled ranged in size from 50 to 304. Each of the companies investigated had a mean of 106 workers.

Table 2 company's size

size	50-100	101-151	152-202	203-253	254-304
Number of workers	2	20	35	49	99

Source: Field Survey

4.4. Participant Profile

Participant Profile table 3 depicts a listing of the highest-ranking officers who completed the survey as part of their business enterprises.

Table 3 Profile

Highest-ranking officers	CEO	CTO	COO	Others
Participate	188	4	7	6

Source: Field Survey

4.5. Descriptive Statistics

4.5.1. Measures

This research used two independent variables; Management Innovations (MI) and technological innovation (TI), one dependent variable named organization performance and sustainably as a mediating variable.

Table 4 Descriptive data for the ten latent variables that are displayed.

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. deviation
PDI	205	2	5	3.67	0.802
PCI	205	1	5	3.23	0.648
FP	205	1	5	3.823	0.854
IC	205	2	5	3.09	0.808
TMS	205	2	5	4.24	0.559
OLC	205	3	5	3.75	0.651
CC	205	2	5	4.09	0.512
CI	205	2	5	3.95	0.695
EI	205	1	5	3.89	0.638
EN	205	1	5	3	0.771

Source: Field Survey

Table 5 Product Innovation Multiple Regression Models and An antecedent these coefficients

1	Model	Understanlized coefficients		Standardized coefficients Beta	T	Sig
	(constant)	-1.164	0.302	0.0235	-5348	0.000
IC	0.167	0.045	0.168	-0.240	3.689	0.000
TMS	0.239	0.073	-0.101	-0.101	-0.2362	0.001
OLC	0.013	0.054	-0.010	-0.102	3.265	0.001

CC	0.253	0.087	0.182	0.26	-0.11	0.001
CI	0.154	0.051	0.152	-0.236	-0.100	0.003
EI	0.198	0.632	0.150	3.000	0.366	0.006
EN	0.362	0.013	0.91	-0.264	-0.3644	0.022

Source: Field Survey

One of the primary goals of this investigation is to identify the motivations of innovations in products.

5. Discussion

However, MI has been identified as a key influence, particularly in emerging economies. In terms of the role of TI, our findings concluded that TI is a critical aspect that improves enterprise sustainability and competitive advantage. Furthermore, it was said that TI enhances many internal and external organizational processes and systematically considerably increases company value sustainability.

5.1. The effect of Invention Precursors on Company Performance

The mediation evaluation revealed that any immediate correlation between innovative precursors and business success is negligible. These seven prior factors, on the other conjunction, have a secondary effect on business performance via innovation in goods and processes.

Table 6 The impacts of innovation precursor on business performance

Variable	Path with PDI	Path with PCI	Total effect on FP
IC	0.173	n.s*	0.0448994
CC	0.18	0.246	0.145688
TMS	0.15	n.s*	0.1466923
OLC	0.15	0.168	0.159733
CI	n.s*	0.55	0.15645
EN	0.463	0.189	0.196136
EI	0.154	0.316	0.164947

Source: Field Survey

5.2. Service to customers a multifunctional framework for IT service-related innovation

The IT services market is continually evolving, and to be successful in this industry, players must innovate. This is not limited to introducing a single service innovation, but to be able to continuously churn out improvements in services supplied in order to maintain competitive advantage.

The capacity to innovate is a capability that companies have to varied degrees. This ability to innovate is what drives business-wide behaviors that lead to methodical innovation activities within the organization.

Again, the innovation capability is multifaceted, and businesses that build and invest in these capacities purposefully and consistently have a greater chance of achieving a consistent stream of inventions.

It has been proposed that service innovation manifests itself in several aspects. Most of the time, these dimensions are interconnected, and intentional adjustments in one dimension generate changes in others.

The current investigation's fundamental aims were to more likely figure out the antecedents for advancement in tiny IT companies as well as the presenting outcomes of invention.

Human Resources, a substantial variable, have been shown to have a link with company execution caused by Development Limit in an evaluation of IT (data innovation) endeavors done in Asia.

6. Conclusion

The transactional backbones of all business organizations are IT-enabled procedures. Today, data and information analysis facilitated by IT improves decision making at all levels of enterprises. Because of the high level of technical skill necessary to provide IT services, such services are frequently outsourced, that is, acquired from businesses that specialize in providing such services.

IT service providers serve as important facilitators of corporate strategy in the emerging knowledge economy. Rapid changes define the IT services market. These changes are multifaceted. Some of these are technical in nature. For example, the software products on which IT applications are constructed are often upgraded, and new goods with a high rate of obsolescence enter the market on a regular basis.

Other fundamental changes brought about by radical notions like open source software and software as a service need dramatic adjustments in the pricing of software goods. Changes in the regulatory environment, such as those brought about by the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002, affect corporate governance and, as a result, information management procedures.

Pricing innovation for software consumption has once again taken several shapes. The most popular payment method is per minute of usage. However, web-based software usage can adopt industry-specific calculation schemas for pricing. A good example would be the use of transportation route optimizer services from companies, which are charged according on the number of cars in the fleet. Depending on the business, the use measure used to determine price may vary greatly.

Given the value of Management Innovations and technological innovation in our research, it is suggested organizations prioritize their own internal resources (hence referred to as MI and TI) in order to achieve outstanding outcomes. The findings demonstrated the value of both innovation in goods and processes.

Future work

Future research may look at the statistical compatibility between innovation in goods and processes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest declared by the researchers.

Statement of informed consent

A thorough framework of ethical issues was carefully followed. All participants gave their consent after being fully informed. The confidentiality of their answers and their voluntary participation were protected for the participants.

References

- [1] Ahlstrom, D. (2010). Innovation and growth: How business contributes to society. *The Academy of Management Perspectives*, 24(3), 11–24. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.24.3.11>
- [2] Berkhout, F. (2011). Adaptation to climate change by organizations. *John Wiley & Son s, Ltd.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.154>
- [3] Dereli, D. D. (2015). Innovation Management in Global Competition and Competitive Advantage. *World Conference on Technology, Innovation and Entrepreneurship* (pp. 1365 – 1370). Istanbul: Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences . <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.06.323>
- [4] Dutta, S. (2012). *The Global Innovation Index 2012 Stronger Innovation Linkages for Global Growth*. The Global Innovation Index 2012. <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org/userfiles/file/GII-2012-Report.pdf>
- [5] Farida, I., & Setiawan, D. (2022). Business Strategies and Competitive Advantage: The Role of Performance and Innovation. *Journal Open Innovation Technology Market and Complexity*, 8(163), 2-16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8030163>

- [6] Janjić, I., & Radjenovic, T. (2019). The importance of managing innovation in modern enterprises. *Ekonomika*, 65(3), 45-54. <http://www.ekonomika.org.rs>
- [7] Klaas, J., & Baggaley, J. (2003). Online Polling as a Collaborative Tool. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 4(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v4i2.138>
- [8] Lee, J., Kim, D., & Sung, S. (2019). The Effect of Entrepreneurship on Start-Up Open Innovation: Innovative Behavior of University Students. *Journal Open Innovation Technology Market Complexity*, 5(103), 2-13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc5040103>
- [9] Lema, R., Kraemer-Mbula, E., & Rakas, M. (2021). Innovation in developing countries: examining two decades of research. *Innovation and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2157930X.2021.1989647>
- [10] OECD. (2016). Innovating Education and Educating for Innovation: The Power of Digital Technologies. *Educational Research and Innovation*. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org/education/ceri/GEIS2016-Background-document.pdf>
- [11] Shea, P. S., & Yanow, D. (2011). *Interpretive Research Design Concepts and Processes*. New York: Routledge.
- [12] Taneja, S., Pryor, M. G., & Hayek, M. (2016). Leaping innovation barriers to small business longevity. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 37(3), 44-51. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBS-12-2014-0145>
- [13] Verhoef, P. C., Broekhuizen, T., Bart, Y., Bhattacharya, A., Dong, J. Q., Fabian, N., et al. (2021). Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 889-901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.09.022>
- [14] Vijay, M. V., Mohanraj, D., & Thirumalai, S. (2023). The Effect of Innovation Management on Sustainable Competitive Advantage in Contemporary Organizations. *Scandinavian Journal of Information Systems*, 1450-1454. DOI: 10.5281/SJIS.775174